

WEST VISAYAS STATE UNIVERSITY
College of Education
GRADUATE SCHOOL
Iloilo City

PENIS AND VAGINA'S CONVERSATIONS: A DIALOGIC THEORY GROUNDED ON
ACADEMIC INTERCOURSE OF HUMAN SEXUALITY

A Dissertation Presented to
the Faculty of the Graduate School
College of Education
West Visayas State University
La Paz, Iloilo City

In Partial Fulfilment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Doctor of Philosophy in Science Education
(Biology)

by

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Abstract

Failed human sexuality education leads to premarital sex and early sexual encounters, resulting in teenage and unplanned pregnancies--hindrances to economic success. This study explored the dialogic dynamics of sexuality education in the classroom, examining teacher-student interactions considering their genders. It aimed to identify the subtleties of dialogue, exchanges, liberal or suppressed inhibitions, and the use of metaphorical and playful language, ultimately generating principles and a nascent dialogic theoretical model on human sexuality education. The research design used was the constructivist grounded theory using theoretical sampling of students and teachers in an integrated SpEd school in Kalibo, arranged class observation of human sexuality lessons, in-depth interviews, focused group discussion, audio-video recording, memoing, field notes, and coding. Results revealed that there is a complex interplay between the genders, sociocultural background and other factors influencing the teaching-learning dynamics, shaping the teaching style and molding learning assimilation during human sexuality lessons. Academic interactions on human sexuality between teachers and students across gender combinations highlighted important aspects such as gender dynamics, language choices, societal norms, humor, reactions, and tolerance, affecting the formation of a safe and comfortable environment, unique to each interacting gender combinations, for discussing sensitive topics. Finally, the generated theory, *The Dialogic*

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Theory on Human Sexuality Education offers a comprehensive framework emphasizing open dialogue, respect, and inclusivity in the classroom. It highlights the importance of creating a safe environment, using respectful language and humor, addressing and challenging societal norms, taboos, and gender stereotypes, and employing varied teaching strategies to cater to diverse perspectives and individual needs. The study ultimately provided a policy guidance for an inclusive and effective scheme in conducting human sexuality education.

Keywords: *dialogic theory on human sexuality education, human sexuality education, penis and vagina's conversations, academic interactions on sexuality, stereotypes in human sexuality education*

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